

POWDER METALLURGY OF STAINLESS STEEL - TUNGSTEN CARBIDE COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY

Stainless steel matrix composites particulate-reinforced with tungsten carbide were successfully fabricated by powder metallurgy route. A variety of processing parameters, i.e. WC content, sintering temperature and holding time, were carried out. The composites' specimens were subjected to testing and characterisation.

Keywords: metal matrix composite, stainless steel, tungsten carbide, powder metallurgy, hardness

INTRODUCTION

Powder metallurgy (P/M) is a well-known process, which can produce materials that have high melting temperature as well as make small and complex-shaped components with precision in dimension and high productivity [1]. It also has advantages in materials and energy saving. The fabrication routes can be either a simply compacting or a, recently developed, metal injection moulding [2]. Stainless steels are extensively used as parts or devices in automobile and chemical industries as well as parts or devices for medical applications because of their ability of corrosion resistance. A variety of hard particles had been added into the stainless steel matrix in order to improve the mechanical properties, such as hardness or wear resistance of this material. The effects of types and contents of reinforcing materials and the sintering conditions were studied in the past decade [3-6]. The present work aims to fabricate stainless steel composites reinforced with tungsten carbide particles by powder metallurgy route. The effect of processing parameters on the microstructure and properties of the composites will be investigated.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Stainless steel powder, used in the present study, was AISI 316L. Tungsten carbide (WC) powder were kindly supplied by SV Nittan Co., Ltd. The two starting powders were subjected to characterisations. Particle size distribution and powder morphology were observed by particle size analyzer and scanning electron microscopy, respectively. Stainless steel powders were mixed with various amounts of tungsten carbide (WC) powders (at 5%, 10% or 15% by weight), Afterwards, the powder mixtures were uniaxially compacted at 300 MPa. Specimens were sintered in hydrogen atmosphere, at

1200 °C, 1250 °C or 1300 °C with a holding time of either 30, 45 or 60 minutes. Specimens of 316L stainless steel powder without any WC addition were also fabricated with the same process. Sintered density of the composites were measured using Archimedes technique. Hardness testing was performed using Rockwell hardness equipment with the indenter of scale A, made of tungsten carbide in a shape of cone. A microstructural study was carried out using both optical microscope and scanning electron microscope.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The particle size data, obtained from a laser particle size analyzer, showed that the 316L and WC powders had a median size (D_{50}) of $\sim 53 \mu\text{m}$ and $\sim 3 \mu\text{m}$, respectively. Figures 1(a) and (b) correspondingly present scanning electron micrograph of 316L and WC powders. The 316L powders had irregular shape due to its fabrication route by water atomization technique. WC powders were agglomerated because they were very fine. It was thought that the finer particle size of WC could fill in the void between the stainless steel particles and resulting in an improvement of the powder packing behaviour.

Figure 1: SEM images of (a) 316L powder (b) WC powder

The microstructure of a sintered specimen at 15% wt WC, 1200 °C for 30 minutes is shown in Figure 2. It was found that 316L powders were sintered and WC powders were agglomerated to be larger particles (lighter phase). Increasing the WC content generally increased the hardness value of the specimens at all sintering temperatures and all times. Figures 3 (a) and (b) present the effect of WC content on hardness of specimens sintered at 1200 °C, 1250 °C and 1300 °C for 30 and 60 minutes, respectively. The higher sintering temperatures also led to higher hardness for all holding times. However, there is no statistically significant difference [7] on the hardness values of composite specimens sintered with various holding times.

Figure 2: SEM image of a sintered specimen containing 15 wt% of WC

(a) holding time 30 minutes

(b) holding time 60 minutes

Figure 3: Hardness of specimens with various WC contents and sintering temperatures with holding times of (a) 30 minutes and (b) 60 minutes

Besides the higher values of hardness, achieved by sintering at elevated temperature, the micrograph reveals that specimen also had high porosity. The optical micrograph of specimen containing 15 wt% of WC, sintered at 1300 °C for 60 minutes is illustrated in Figure 4. From the present work, it was observed that porosity decreased and sintering shrinkage increased when specimens were sintered at higher temperature. The linear shrinkage was approximately 3 %. The sintered densities of specimens were in the range of 6.5 - 6.7 g/cm³ (85% of theoretical value). Further investigation should be carried out to improve the sintered density. Changing the particle size of the powders in order to obtain a good packing density as well as adjusting the sintering conditions i.e. atmosphere, temperature or time might be helpful for the improvement of the sintered properties. The composite specimens will also be subjected to salt spray test to study corrosion behaviour and wear test to study the wear behaviour of the composites.

Figure 4: Optical micrograph of a specimen, containing 15 wt% of WC, sintered at 1300 °C for 60 minutes

CONCLUSIONS

Powder metallurgy technique can be employed for a fabrication of stainless steel-tungsten carbide metal matrix composites. However, the composite specimens had high porosity. Hardness was increased with increasing WC contents at all temperatures and times conducted in the present work. Higher sintering temperature led to an increase in hardness and a reduction of porosity. Nonetheless, the effect of holding time on the hardness value did not show any statistically significant difference. The highest value of hardness was gained from specimens, containing 15 wt% of WC, sintered at 1300 °C.

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